

WORK-LIFE BALANCE: EXPLORING THE LIVED-EXPERIENCES OF COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH PART-TIME JOBS

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the lived of experiences of college students with part-time jobs. It is a qualitative in nature, focusing on the personal experiences of the students. The samples consists of 25 college students with part-time jobs from different department. The primary data-gathering method was a survey interview using structured questions. The data were analyzed through thematic analysis. The results revealed several themes regarding the lived experiences of college students with part-time jobs. This include factors influencing students' decisions to take on part-time jobs; financial support, to gain work experiences and skills development. Strategies students use to balance academic responsibilities and part-time jobs; time management and scheduling, prioritizing self-care and maintaining open communication. Challenges faced in maintaining work-life balance; sleep deprivation, sacrificing socialization, work-study conflicts, and physical and mental exhaustion. Additionally, students cope with stress by seeking support, pursuing hobbies, taking rest and positive thinking and resilience. The study recommends that students proactively develop and continually refine their time management and self-care practices. They should seek support from peers, academic advisers, and workplace mentors while maintaining open communication to effectively manage their multiple responsibilities. Cultivating resilience and adopting positive coping strategies are also essential to achieving a healthy work-life balance.

Keywords: Work-life balance, College students, Part-time jobs, Lived-experiences

Introduction

Work-life balance is an essential part of well-being, especially for college students who balance academic duties and part-time work. The rising cost of higher education and the desire for financial independence have prompted many college students to work part-time while pursuing their academic aspirations. This dual job brings both opportunities and problems, as students must balance the demands of work and education. While employment can give financial security and essential skills, it frequently comes at the expense of increased stress, lower academic focus, and decreased emotional well-being. The concept of work-life balance is essential for understanding how students manage these

overlapping demands. The number of college students with part-time job has been increasing rapidly over the years. Part-time jobs are common among college students who needs to earn an extra income to support their educational and financial needs. Students have different motivations for working, such as fulfilling financial obligations like covering tuition and rent, acquiring experience relevant to their career aspirations, and earning extra money (Remenick & Bergman, 2021).

Recent research has emphasized the complexities of this subject. While part-time employment can help students improve their time management and organizational skills, it also limits

flexibility and has a negative influence on mental health and social life when schedules get too hectic (Summer et al., 2023).

College students face a variety of challenges, including time management, stress management, and balancing work and school obligations (Tumin et al., 2020). Part-time job has an impact on university students' daily life and learning experiences. It might affect students' study habits, social interactions, and even their financial condition (Mai Huynh Thanh Nhi, 2022). Moreover, financial constraints require many students to work long hours, making it difficult to balance academic and personal obligations (Paulson, 2024). Working while studying has proven difficult for many students to balance their academic and part-time job obligations (Tus et al., 2022).

Furthermore, students must work while learning since their parents have insufficient financial resources to support their studies, demonstrating the relationship between education and financial necessities. One of the primary reasons why many students juggle part-time job and studies is to produce an income to cover their personal and academic expenses. A study discovered that students who work are more likely to have financial difficulties and worry about paying for their education than those who do not work, because they have to balance work and education, they take fewer units. Working students are apparently less likely to attend classes and more likely to suffer from mental health issues. Given these challenges, it is critical to consider how working students manage and balance their time with academic responsibilities (Soria et al., 2020).

Most students said they worked to support their families and cover expenses. The bulk

of students have chosen mundane part-time jobs with no relevance to their future careers. The students stated that their sleep deprivations were caused by their inability to balance work and study, which had a negative impact on their academic performance as well as their physical and mental health (Venulava & Jorbenadze, 2022).

Several studies have looked into the relationship between college students' GPAs (grade point averages) and part-time jobs, with some finding a negative correlation. Students who work part-time may realize that they do not have enough time to study. Furthermore, time constraints may have an impact on their participation and academic success. Students frequently find jobs in the hotel or retail industries. Jobs in these industries, particularly those in restaurants, frequently require working late. Students may thus be unable to fully participate in their classes the next day, or they may choose to avoid them entirely (Kremers, 2021). Part-time employment in the academic life of university students is becoming increasingly widespread as socioeconomic situations and educational environments change (Taylor et al., 2020).

Part-time employment among students today is the result of a complex interaction between financial demands, growing college costs, and a proactive desire to learn real-world skills related to their subject of study (Evans, 2020). 361 Egyptian university students discovered that work stress and poor work-life balance were directly related to emotional exhaustion. Due to sleep deprivation and time constraints, students working more than 20 hours per week reported a 30% rise in academic disengagement. To reduce crossover stress, the study proposed that companies provide flexibility, such as

scheduling shifts around exams (Fauziah et al., 2024).

Students who worked more than 20 hours per week experienced a 15-20% decline in GPA when compared to their colleagues who did not work (Luu et al., 2023). In a 2022 cross-sectional study of 610 undergraduates, 61% worked 18 hours per week on average as part-time employment due to a financial need. Sleep deprivation caused by night employment has been connected to a 44% decline in academic performance and an increase in physical health risks (such as headaches and obesity). The report proposed that universities provide flexible scheduling and time management training (Verulava & Jorbenadze, 2022).

Other studies, however, show that working part-time offers advantages. Students will perform better academically if they take more part-time occupations related to their degree (Danh Luu Chi et al., 2023). It is worth noting that some studies have identified potential benefits to working part-time. According to a student-focused study, part-time employees' work experience can improve their academic performance. The study stressed the importance of time management and argued that, with adequate management, part-time employment could be beneficial (Azis & Yusanti, 2021). The majority of students stated that having a job was essential since it allowed them to provide financial support to their families and cover expenses (Ngan, 2021).

Part-time work may have a negative impact on academic progress and cause health concerns due to the added stress and time management challenges it entails. These issues could have long-term effects for students' academic achievement and overall well-being. Students must also

navigate the numerous challenges that come with working part-time. Working while pursuing college education can assist students improve their employability skills such as teamwork, time management, customer service, and interpersonal communication. Part-time job has a significant favorable impact on academic attainment (Linggasari & Kurniawan, 2020).

Students' academic performance will improve when they pursue more part-time jobs related to their degree (Liu Chi Danh et al., 2023). A student-focused study revealed that part-time workers can achieve good or even greater academic performance as a result of the experience they gain from their jobs. The study emphasized the importance of time management and suggested that part-time work could be beneficial if done effectively (Azis & Yusanti, 2021).

Part-time work has a multifaceted impact on university students' academic performance, which is affected by a number of factors including the number of hours worked, the nature of the job, and students' ability to manage their time well. While there is evidence of negative outcomes, particularly when working hours are high, some research suggests that part-time work may provide valuable experience that, when done right, might improve academic success. Studying while working has no discernible effect on student academic achievement. However, it is entirely dependent on the student who is experiencing it. Working part-time has no effect on lectures or academic achievement as long as students can manage their time well (Choo et al., 2021).

The majority of studies on work-life balance among college students with part-time jobs primarily use quantitative survey

designs that only measure variables like work hours, academic performance, and stress levels without going into much detail about the students' individual experiences. In particular, existing studies frequently ignores how students personally experience and manage the factors that influence their decision to take on part-time jobs, the strategies they use to balance academics and work, the challenges they face, and the ways they cope with stress. This emphasizes the necessity of qualitative approaches, which can offer a more thorough and in-depth understanding of these experiences than can be obtained just by quantitative methods. This study explores the lived experiences of college students with part time jobs as they manage the complications of juggling work and academic responsibilities. The said study also aims to reveal these student's distinct perspectives. By giving light on these experiences, this study intends to provide useful insights into the realities of working college students. Understanding these lived experiences is critical for building an environment in which students can achieve academically while balancing the demands of work during their college years.

Objectives

This study generally aimed to explore the lived experiences of college students with part-time jobs. This study answered the central question: How do college students with part-time jobs describe their lived experiences of balancing work and academic responsibilities?

Specifically, it would answer the following sub-questions:

1. What factors influence students' decisions to take on part-time jobs?

2. What strategies do students use to balance academic responsibilities and part-time jobs?

3. What are challenges do students face in maintaining work-life balance?

4. How do students cope with stress related to juggling multiple responsibilities?

Methods

This study employed a qualitative-phenomenological research design to explore the lived-experiences of college students with part-time jobs. Qualitative research is an appropriate method in this study as it allows the participants to share their stories and experiences in their own words (Levitt et al., 2018). Phenomenology was particularly suited for capturing the essence and meaning of participants' personal experiences, focusing on how they perceived and interpreted the challenges and strategies involved in balancing part-time jobs and academic responsibilities (Amzat et al., 2021). By using this method, the researcher was able to gather rich, detailed narratives that highlights the challenges of work-life balance from the students' own perspectives.

This study was conducted at one of the private tertiary schools. Students are currently enrolled in college as well as working part-time. Researchers gathered sufficient and relevant information as well as evidence for the environment, which is very fit and suited for the research conducted.

The Purposive-Criterion sampling technique was used to choose a sample of participants who met certain criteria that were necessary to the study. This is a non-probability sampling method that involves choosing participants based on certain characteristics that are important to the study (Palinkas et al., 2015). The

researchers are interested in participants who can give them a lot of useful information about how they balance their part-time jobs and academic responsibilities. The researcher is in charge of putting together a sample that meets these criteria to make sure that the data collected is varied and useful.

The research participants in this study were selected using purposive-criterion sampling, a non-probability sampling method in which participants are chosen on purpose based on certain criteria that are important to the research objectives (Teflpedia, n.d. 2024). In particular, the sample consisted of 25 college students with part-time jobs and were currently enrolled in the academic year 2024-2025 at a private tertiary school. This sampling approach allowed the researchers to focus on participants who could provide rich and relevant insights into their lived experiences balancing academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. By applying these criteria, the study made sure that the data collected was useful and closely aligned to its aim of exploring work-life balance among college students with part-time jobs (Palinkas et al., 2015).

The researchers are considered the main instruments of the study and are guided by an interview guide questionnaire. The survey interview questions were created by the researchers before collecting the essential data. Using the study's central question, the researchers gave significant thought to formulating the survey interview guide questions as a preliminary step. Essentially, the critical questions gathered all the data for analysis. To allow the participants to freely discuss and share their experiences and insights, open-ended questions were asked. To ensure that the questions and analysis were consistent with the research study, they were validated by

an expert. The responses to the survey questions provided the preliminary data that were examined and interpreted. The researchers employed a survey interview questionnaire to collect data, which was designed with a collection of orderly structured questions. Participants used the language they were most comfortable with to express and share their experiences clearly.

During the data collection, the following tasks were completed, and the researchers secured official approval from the deans of five departments. A letter addressed to each dean was submitted, requesting permission to conduct research on the lived experiences of college students with part-time jobs. Before collecting the data, the researchers created a survey interview guide questionnaire with carefully constructed questions based on the central question. The data collected served as the primary basis for data analysis and interpretation. Experts validated and approved the survey interview guide questionnaire. After receiving approval from each dean, the researchers conducted a survey of five selected college students with part-time jobs from each department across all year levels.

The respondents were informed that all information and data they provided would be treated with strict confidentiality. Participation was completely voluntary, and the respondents could withdraw their participation at any time.

The data were analyzed using Thematic Analysis, developed by Braun and Clarke (2006). This method involved identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns or themes within qualitative data. The analysis followed six key steps. First, the researchers familiarized themselves with the data by transcribing and repeatedly

reading the material to gain a deep understanding. Second, they generated initial codes by systematically labeling significant features of the data. Third, the researchers searched for themes by grouping related codes into broader patterns. Fourth, they reviewed the themes to ensure coherence and that they accurately represented the data. Fifth, the themes were defined and named clearly to capture their essence. Finally, the researchers produced a report presenting the themes and supporting them with data to convey meaningful insights. This structured approach provided a rigorous and flexible framework for interpreting the qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Result and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings obtained from the survey conducted on the topic of work-life balance among college students who have part-time jobs. The data collected provides valuable insights into how these students manage their academic responsibilities and part-time jobs.

Factors Influencing Students' Decision to Engage in Part-time Job

For many students, the decision to work in part-time jobs is a significant choice, and it is influenced by several factors. Based on the data gathered by the researchers, students were influenced by the need for financial support, to gain work experience and the opportunity to develop skills.

Financial support

The resources students require to pay for tuition, living expenses, and other study-related fees are referred to as financial support. In order to fulfill these financial obligations, many students are motivated to work part-time because parental aid and scholarships frequently do

not cover all costs. Students who work part-time can reduce their dependency on family support by earning money for necessities like food, books, transportation, and personal needs. The following were common responses among participants:

“Dako ug impact for me as a student ang mag part-time job, makakuha ka ug extra allowance, then through this mcover nako akong transportation, food ug school materials.” [Having a part-time job has a big impact for me as a student, because I can get extra allowance from it and I can cover my expenses like transportation, foods and school materials.] P22

“Naglisod gyud mi kay walay stable nga trabaho akong mga ginikanan maong nisulod ko ug part-time job bisag kapoy para naay pambayad sa tuition.” [My parents do not have a stable job that is why I took part-time job to pay my tuition fees even though its tiring.] P10

Research reveals that there are several factors on why many students were motivated to engage on a part-time jobs. One of the reasons is financial support. Students are influenced to work part-time because they want to cover college fees such as tuition, bills and other necessities. Financial support is the key reason why students are motivated to engage themselves on a part-time jobs to support their financial needs (Azis & Yusanti, 2021). Furthermore, the main factor that serves as the driving force to students to

work part-time is to achieve a financial independence and ensuring that they have a steady income that would help them to sustain their academic and daily expenses (Prasad & Pasupathi, 2022).

To Gain Work Experiences and the Opportunity to Develop Skills

Students are motivated to work part-time not just to support their financial needs but also to gain work experiences and the opportunity to develop skills. The following are some common responses among participants:

“Wala gyud koy financial concern, ang ako lang is magpart-time lang to gain experience. It is an opportunity, ako ra pong gigrab since duol siya sa akong course.” [Honestly, I do not have financial concerns, I just pursue part-time job to gain experiences. It is an opportunity; I grab since it is related to my program.] P25

“Gusto ko makakat-on ug experience, mapractice akong skills, ug makatabang sa akong kaugalingon sa umaabot.” [I want to acquire experiences, develop my skills that would help me in the future.] P22

“Experience, since related man akong work sa akong program so nakatabang jud to gain knowledge og skills like time management og communication.” [The experience, since my work is related to my program, it

helps me to gain knowledge and skills like time-management and communication skills.] P23

The participants' responses revealed that working part-time while studying provides students with knowledge gained from their work experiences. Part-time jobs provides students with hands-on experience and help them develop valuable skills such as communication, managing time effectively which are essentials for their future careers (Pham, 2024). Experiences students gained from their work helps build confidence and responsibility for students, it enhances their capabilities as a student while working (Billet, 2005). Moreover, gaining work experiences and the opportunity to develop skills are essential factors that motivates students to engaged on a part-time jobs. They are not just working to support their financial needs, students are also take on a part-time jobs because it is related to their courses. (Zhou & Chen, 2021).

Strategies for Balancing Academic and Work

For students who take part-time jobs while studying, they used strategies to complete their task and to balance their multiple responsibilities. Based on the data gathered, participants make sure to utilized effective way such as time management and scheduling in completing their task in both school and work, open communication and prioritizing self-care.

Time Management and Scheduling

Time management and scheduling are the purposeful processes of arranging and planning how to divide time between various tasks and obligations with the objective of increasing productivity and maintaining balance, particularly for

students who work both academically and part-time. The following were common responses among participants:

“Ang strategy nga akong gihimo is time management gyud magset ko ug schedule sa akong mga trabahoon, mosayo ko ug mata sa buntag around 4am dayon buhaton nako akong trabaho tanan and depende nalang kung unsa ka hectic akong achedules.” [The strategy I implemented is time management. I set a schedule for my tasks, wake up early in the morning around 4 AM, and then complete all my work. It ultimately depends on how hectic my schedule becomes.] P1

“As a student with part-time job, I always try to balance my time between school work and job and I set schedules for every task.” P5

“For me, as a hair and make-up artist assistant, as I work on the industry of make-up. I always manage my time properly and make sure that the slots and bookings that I have will not affect my studies. During class hours, I do not accept any bookings except weekends.” P6

“I plan my schedules and manage my time. Kung time sa trabaho, magfocus jud ko sa trabaho, kung time naman para magtoon, maggahin jud ko ug time

para sa pagtoon.” [I plan my schedules and manage my time. During work hours, I focus entirely on work. When it is time to study, I dedicate specific hours to studying.] P25

The participants’ responses emphasized that time management and scheduling is critical for balancing academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. They highlighted structured scheduling and using planners, calendars, or digital tools to organize assignments and shifts. Students focusing on urgent tasks like deadlines or exams first, while reserving less critical activities for later. Role-specific boundaries, such as declining work bookings during class hours or separating work and study blocks, were also key to avoiding overlaps and maintaining academic performance. Additionally, proactive planning were deemed essential. Students stressed the importance of studying during vacant hours, avoiding cramming by preparing days in advance for exams, and multitasking roles like leadership positions without compromising priorities. Tools like planners helped them track obligations, while self-discipline ensured adherence to schedules despite hectic demands. Good time management and prioritization are critical to student achievement, particularly when managing academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Time management strategies play a crucial role in student success, allowing students to balance scholastic expectations with work and other responsibilities (Carless, 2008).

Open Communication

It is the practice of actively sharing information, expectations, and concerns

with others in order to foster understanding and support, particularly when juggling academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Open communication involves regularly informing employers about class schedules, upcoming exams, or academic deadlines, and likewise updating teachers or professors about work commitments that may affect attendance or submission of assignments. The following are some common responses among participants:

"Kapoy jod siya, instead of Sunday nga time para ipahulay mahimo na pod nga time para magtoon kay for example monday naay exam, makaadjust raman ko kay ma estoryahan nako akong amo then through that maadjust nako akong schedules." [It is really tiring. Instead of Sunday being a time to rest, it becomes a time to study, especially if there is an exam on Monday. But I can adjust because I can talk to my boss, and through that, I can adjust my schedule.] P9

"Kadaghan na gyud nahitabo nga nakaapekto ang trabaho sa akong pag-skwela. Nagahangyo rako sa among instructor to catch up." [Many times, work has affected my studies. I just ask our instructor to allow me to catch up on the activities that I missed.] P10

"Naay times nga malate ko ug pass sa akong mga activity pero okay raman sab kay makahangyo raman mi sa among instructor." [There are times when I submitted my activities late, but it is okay because we can negotiate with our instructor to allow us to catch up and submit.] P12

Students who managed both academic responsibilities and part-time jobs highlighted open communication as a vital conflict-resolution approach. Many participants mentioned communicating with employers and instructors to change work hours or deadlines, such as telling bosses about test dates that require shift or obtaining extensions from instructors when job obligations conflicted with study. Students can avoid burnout and academic consequences if they openly share their limits with employers and instructors. This method not only relieves tension, but it also creates a support network that recognizes their multiple responsibilities. Effective open communication is widely recognized as a vital method for managing academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Open communication with employers and instructors enables students to manage expectations, resolve issues, and guarantee alignment between their career and educational commitments (Ugoji, R., 2024).

Prioritizing Self-care

It entails consciously allocating time and attention to promote one's physical, emotional, and mental well-being. In the midst of hectic schedules and conflicting expectations, self-care is frequently ignored, yet it is critical for maintaining balance and avoiding burnout. Individuals who engage in self-care activities, such as getting adequate sleep, eating good meals, exercising, practicing mindfulness, or simply relaxing, can better manage stress, reduce anxiety, and enhance their overall mood and resilience. Far from being selfish, emphasizing self-care allows people to recharge, making them better equipped to face life's obstacles. The following are some common responses among participants:

"Importante kaayo ang pag amping sa kaugalingon to prevent illness kay kung dili nimo ampingon imong kaugalingon maglisod ka og balance sa responsibilities nimo kung magsakit ka."
[Self-care is very important to prevent illness because if you do not take care of yourself, it is hard to balance your responsibilities when you get sick.] P2

"Personal care, importante kaayo siya sa pagbalance sa akong multiple responsibilities like matulog og mokaon sa saktong oras." [Personal care is very important for balancing my multiple responsibilities, like sleeping and eating on time.] P7

The participants' responses cited self-care as an important strategy. They emphasized the need of enough sleep and intentional rest in maintaining physical and mental health, pointing out that disregarding these habits leads to burnout and reduces productivity. Others related self-care directly to physical fitness, claiming that staying healthy is essential for managing rigorous schedules. Ignoring personal well-being impairs one's ability to meet academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Balancing job and education needs more than just scheduling; it also necessitates purposeful self-care to maintain health and vitality. Students stated that getting enough sleep and rest is vital for avoiding burnout and remaining productive. Ignoring personal well-being, results in poor performance, illness, and difficulties in completing multiple obligations. Thus, thriving in dual roles

requires a holistic approach that includes disciplined preparation as well as constant self-care (De Leon, M. A. ,2024).

Challenges in Maintaining Work-life Balance

Students balancing academic responsibilities and part-time jobs often face challenges in maintaining a healthy work-life balance. Based on the gathered data, common challenges include sleep deprivation, sacrificing socialization, work-study conflict, as well as physical and mental exhaustion.

Sleep Deprivation

It refers to the condition in which an individual does not get enough sleep, which has a significant impact on their ability to function effectively. Sleep deprivation disrupts the process of rest and recovery, leading to reduced cognitive abilities, diminished concentration, and increased irritability. For students balancing academic responsibilities and part-time jobs, lack of sleep makes it challenging to stay focused and complete tasks efficiently. The following are some common responses among participants:

"Sometimes I cannot focus on my work, especially when there is an exam and at school the instructor get mad at me because I fall asleep in class. I cannot sleep at night because I have so much responsibilities like school works and also house chores." P3

"My very big challenge is the lack of sleep, naa koy daghang responsibilities like pagbalance sa akong part-time work and study pa, so sa morning naa koy

work and study at night, bisan ug kapoy dili sa jud ko matulog kay naa pay daghang tiwasonon like asignments ug tun-anan especially kung naay exam ug quizzes pagka ugma.” [My biggest challenge is the lack of sleep. I have many responsibilities, like balancing my part-time work and my studies. In the morning, I work, and I study at night. Even when I am tired, I do not go to sleep right away because I still have a lot to finish, like assignments and lessons to study, especially when there are exams and quizzes the next day.] P4

Balancing part-time work and academic duties can be difficult due to sleep deprivation, according to students. Participants reported difficulty focusing at work or in class frequently staying awake late to finish assignments, study for tests, or handle overlapping obligations such as school activities and job expectations. Sleep deprivation has a negative impact on students' academic and part-time work performance. A lack of rest causes less focus, slower cognitive performance, and increased tension, making it difficult to fulfill deadlines or retain information (Abidi, A., 2023).

Sacrificing Socialization

This relates to the requirement for students to reduce or discontinue social activities, gatherings, or time spent with friends in order to meet academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Many students find themselves spending weekends or spare time studying or

working rather than socializing, especially when curriculum is difficult or job schedules are rigid. While this sacrifice might help students meet deadlines and sustain academic achievement, it frequently results in missed social experiences, relaxation, and opportunity to create relationships. 2 out of 25 participants stated that they experienced sacrificing socialization as a challenge in maintaining work-life balance. The following are some common responses among participants:

“One of the challenge I have encountered in maintaining work-life balance is I have to make sacrifices, such as reducing social activities like hang out with friends.”
P1

“Tungod sa kadaghan sa mga buluhaton, maglisod napod ko ug pangita ug time nga makalaag with my friends. Naglisod naman gani ko ug balance sa akong work and studies, what more pa sa akong socialization.” [Because of the overwhelming amount of tasks, I struggle to find time to hang out with my friends. I'm already having a hard time balancing work and studies how much more with my social life?] P2

Students juggling academic responsibilities and part-time jobs frequently identified sacrificing socialization as a significant challenge. Participants reported reducing or eliminating social activities, such as hanging out with friends, due to heavy workloads and tight schedules. Participants expressed frustration at being unable to

allocate time for leisure or relationships, emphasizing that balancing work and studies alone already demands significant effort, leaving little room for social engagement. This sacrifice, while important to meet deadlines and maintain performance, often leads to feelings of isolation and stress, further challenging their capacity to attain a healthy work-life balance. While focusing academics and work helps people stay productive, a lack of social engagement can lead to mental tiredness and a lower quality of life (Sapient Labs, 2023).

Work-Study Conflict

This refers to the difficulty that students encounter when the obligations of their academic commitments and part-time responsibilities overlap or compete, making it difficult to fulfill both positions successfully. Work-study conflict can take the form of time-based confrontations, emotional strain, or behavioral issues, such as being unable to attend courses owing to work shifts or being too weary from a job to concentrate on academics. These tensions frequently result in increased stress, poor academic performance, and an increased risk of burnout as students attempt to achieve both school and employment demands. The following are some common responses among participants:

“Sometimes, I also have a hard time choosing what to prioritize especially when my work and studies are conflicting.” P20

“Because I want to earn money, sometimes I really prioritize my work and sometimes I get late in passing school assignments

and activities and it really affects my grades.” P6

“Yes, nakaexperienced ko ug situation nga naapeketuhan akong studies tungod sa akong job kay naay time nga akong amo dili siya mosugot nga moabsent ko, so wala koy choice kay matanggal man ko sa trabaho if moabsent ko sa akong work, maapektuhan jud ang akong grades.” [Yes, I experienced situations where my studies were affected by my job because there were times when my boss would not allow me to take time off. I had no choice since I would risk losing my job if I skipped work, which directly impacted my grades.] P7

Research reveals that students with part-time employment frequently experience work-study difficulties due to overlapping schedules, rigorous job demands, and weariness. Prioritizing job over academics to preserve money is a major difficulty, resulting in late submissions, worse scores, and unprepared tests. Participants cited strict employers who denied them time off, leading them to miss classes or examinations, as well as the mental and physical strain of managing both roles. Conflicts such as work seminars during lectures or last-minute projects allocated during class hours hampered their academic attention, causing them to struggle to stay up with colleagues. Many underlined the pressure of studying late at night while working early in the morning, which leads to burnout. Work-study conflicts create a cycle of stress and

academic compromise, with students sacrificing grades, sleep, and social well-being to meet dual demands (Ali, R. S. , 2023).

Physical/ Mental Exhaustion

It refers to the overwhelming fatigue both physical and psychological that students feel when striving to balance academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Physical exhaustion can include sleepiness, headaches, sleep difficulties, and changes in food habits, but mental exhaustion is characterized by trouble in concentrating and reduced motivation. These symptoms are frequently the result of lengthy periods of high stress, poor sleep, and the pressure to fulfill various deadlines. The following are some common responses among participants:

“Ang challenge nga akong naencounter is exhaustion, dayon despite ana gitry gyud nako nga makarest.”
[The challenge I have encountered is exhaustion, but despite that, I still try to get some rest.] P8

“As a computer science student ang challenge gyud is moeskwela bitaw nga kapoy ang lawas pero no choice kay kinahanglan gyud mosulod kay daghang mga activities nga kinahanglang apason samot na sa mga hands on activities.” [As a computer science student, the real challenge is attending classes even when my body is exhausted. I have no choice because there are many activities to keep up

with, especially hands-on tasks.] P9

Research shows that students who work part-time and have academic commitments have significant physical and emotional strain, leading to persistent weariness and burnout. Attending lectures and other hands-on work while physically exhausted can leave you with no energy for studying or caring for yourself. Stress worsens during exam periods, with students reporting an inability to retain material despite intensive attempts, aggravated by overlapping job hours and important academic deadlines (Frontiers in Psychology, 2022; LSE, 2025).

Coping with Stress from Multiple Responsibilities

Students who handle both school and a part-time job often feel stressed because of their multiple responsibilities. Based on the gathered data, participants use helpful ways to cope with stress, such as seeking support from friends and family, pursuing hobbies to relax, positive thinking and resilience, and taking breaks to rest.

Seeking Support

This refers to the proactive attitude students take to reduce stress by asking out for support from others when balancing various tasks. Seeking help can mean talking to trusted friends, family members, peers, or experts about academic stress, career commitments, or emotional struggles. By voicing their worries, students can gain perspective, feel less alienated, and receive practical guidance or emotional support. Building a strong support network is critical for coping with stress because it gives students a sense of belonging and access to tools that can help them handle problems more successfully.

The following are some common responses among participants:

“If makaexperience ko ug stress, my support system is akong family and friends through them malessen akong stress nga nafeel kay imotivate man ko nila.” [If I experience stress, my support system is my family and friends. Through them, the stress I feel is lessened because they motivate me.] P1

“Para macope nako ang stress, naa akong friends and family, naa pog koy mga classmates nga andam motabang sa akong mga problems.” [To cope with stress, I have my friends and family, and I also have classmates who are ready to help with my problems.] P2

Pursuing Hobbies

These are deliberate behaviors in which students participate in recreational activities to recharge their minds and emotions while juggling academic responsibilities and part-time job. Pursuing hobbies, such as creative arts, sports, or personal interests, gives an avenue for stress release and a sense of success that is unconnected to academic or professional performance. The following are some common responses among participants:

“Kung kapuyon ko, molantaw ko ug anime movies, basa ug stories and magdula ug mobile games or ML.” [When I am tired, I watch anime movies, read stories, and play mobile

games like Mobile Legends.] P6

“Sa akona, hilig man ko magmountaineering, so if naa koy time magmountaineering ko para dili ra kaayo ko mastress.” [For me, I enjoy mountaineering, so whenever I have time, I go mountain climbing to avoid getting too stressed.] P7

The participants' responses revealed that students with part-time employment engage in a variety of hobbies and leisure activities to relieve stress and recharge from academic and work-related exhaustion. Popular coping mechanisms include watching anime or K-dramas, reading books, playing mobile games like Mobile Legends, listening to music, and participating in sports or outdoor activities like mountaineering. These activities provide a mental getaway, allowing students to momentarily shift their focus away from daily stresses and duties. This has been demonstrated to help reduce stress levels and increase emotional well-being (Malque, 2024).

Positive Thinking and Resilience

These are important psychological traits that help students deal with the stress of juggling multiple responsibilities, such as academics and part-time jobs. Positive thinking entails retaining an optimistic view and focusing on potential solutions rather than obstacles, whereas resilience refers to the ability to recover from setbacks and adapt to difficult circumstances. Together, these qualities empower students to manage adversity, reduce stress, and maintain motivation even when faced with

demanding schedules and competing priorities. The following are some common responses among participants:

“Kinahanglan imotivate nimo imong kaugalingon kay dili sa tanang oras naa imong pamilya na makatabang sa imoha”
[You need to motivate yourself because your family would not always be there to help you.] P3

“For me, hunahunaon ra nako nganong naa ko diri nga sitwasiyon, kay para raman pud ni sa akong kaugalingon ug pamilya and be positive lang always.”
[For me, I just remind myself why I am in this situation, it is for myself and my family and stay positive always.] P9

“Just be positive all the time. Enjoy life and smile kay everything has a solution.”
P11

“Positive thinking and go with the flow lang gihapon bisag nakasab-an na ka. Bisag naay mga negative nga gisulti, ibalewala ra gyud na nako.” [Positive thinking go with the flow even if you have been scolded. Even if there are negative comments, I just ignore them.] P12

The participants' responses revealed that students who work part-time prioritize positivity and resilience, highlighting the importance of developing inner strength due to the unpredictable

nature of external assistance. Maintaining a positive perspective in the face of tiredness or criticism, as well as focusing on personal goals, are important strategies for staying motivated. Students emphasize the significance of self-reliance, believing in their abilities to overcome obstacles and discarding negativity to avoid emotional fatigue. Their strategy emphasizes adaptation, such as "going with the flow" during setbacks (Minha Hossain, 2023).

Taking Breaks

This is the deliberate habit of suspending work or academic duties to rest, refuel, and reset mentally and physically. Taking pauses helps students manage stress by providing a break from continuous concentration, lowering mental weariness, and minimizing burnout. Breaks, whether in the form of short periods of relaxation, physical movement, enable students to return to their responsibilities with more concentration, creativity, and emotional stability.

“Since kakapoy manlang akong nafeel, usahay magrelax ko, magpahuway para dili gyud ko mastress.”
[Since I often feel tired, sometimes I relax or take rest so I do not get stressed.]
P18

“Binon-ugay gyud ang academic ug naa pa gyud kay work so dili siya lalim, maningkamot lang gyud. Dapat naa kay time to rest and magrelax pod panalagsa.” [Balancing academics and work is tough, so I just work hard. But you need to make time to rest and relax occasionally.] P19

“Bisan ug daghan kaayo ko ug responsibilities dili gyud nako kalimtan ang magrelax, naay time to break.” [Even with many responsibilities, I never forget to relax and take breaks.] P24

The participants responses revealed that in order to avoid burnout, students who work part-time and study actively incorporate rest and relaxation into their routines. They emphasize the importance of taking intentional breaks, such as taking time to rest, socializing with friends, or visiting family. Many students describe feeling overwhelmed during peak periods, such as exams, but counteract this by prioritizing downtime to recharge (Medanta, 2025).

Conclusion and Recommendation

Students choose part-time jobs mainly due to the need for financial support and the desire to gain work experiences and develop skills. While some students are driven by the chance to improve their time management and communication skills, many students take on part-time jobs to help their parents in paying for personal expenses and tuition.

Students employ a variety of strategies to manage their academic responsibilities and part-time jobs. Effective time management and scheduling enable them to allot enough time for both work and school, while prioritizing self-care helps maintain their physical and mental well-being. Open communication with employers, instructors and family members also supports their ability to manage overlapping commitments and reduce stress.

Students still struggle to maintain a healthy work-life balance in spite of these efforts. Sleep deprivation is common, as students often sacrifice rest to meet their obligations. Sacrificing socialization can cause feelings of isolation, which negatively impacts mental health. Conflicts between work and study force students to make tough decisions, and the added strain frequently leads to mental and physical exhaustion.

Students use a variety of coping mechanisms to manage the stress of balancing multiple responsibilities. They take breaks to recharge, engage in hobbies for personal fulfillment and relaxation, think positively and be resilient, and look for support from peers, family, and coworkers.

Overall, juggling academic responsibilities and a part-time job is difficult, but students demonstrate perseverance in managing these demands. They can minimize negative impacts and keep developing both personally and professionally by putting good strategies into practice and making use of support systems.

Based on the findings mentioned above, the researchers endorse the following recommendation:

1. Students are encouraged to proactively create and regularly update their time management and self-care strategies. They could also seek support from peers and mentors in both academic and workplace settings and remain receptive to feedback to enhance their ability to balance multiple responsibilities effectively.
2. The Dean of the CTE department, teachers and academic advisers are encouraged to provide flexible support, establish open communication, and raise

awareness about the need of self-care and stress management among students who work part-time.

3. Employers might accommodate student workers by providing flexible scheduling, acknowledging academic commitments, and fostering a supportive work atmosphere that recognizes the dual roles of student employees.

4. Future studies are encouraged to look at the long-term impacts of part-time work on academic achievement, mental health, and career development, as well as the efficacy of various support interventions suited to students' diverse needs and backgrounds.

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